

Elongation ability of deepwater rice as affected by age of seedlings. BRRI, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Seedling age (d)	% increase in plant ht	Internode length (cm)	Internodes (no.)
<i>Habiganj Aman II</i>			
10	216	0	0
20	160.5	51.8	3.2
30	130.1	61.8	4.6
40	76.8	48.9	3.8
<i>Habiganj Aman III</i>			
10	177.8	0	0
20	112.8	43.6	2.5
30	134.2	63.0	4.6
40	134.2	49.9	3.6
<i>Habiganj Aman V</i>			
10	203.4	0	0
20	186.8	44.5	2.5
30	140.0	67.0	4.2
40	112.1	56.9	4.6
<i>Habiganj Aman VI</i>			
10	189.1	0	0
20	165.1	49.4	2.5
30	140.9	55.1	3.9
40	104.5	53.0	3.9
<i>Habiganj Aman VII</i>			
10	222.3	0	0
20	145.4	60.6	3.6
30	121.2	68.4	4.2
40	105.9	55.8	4.2

greatest internode length was recorded in 30-day-old seedlings.

It appears that total plant elongation ability and internode elongation ability

are different physiological phenomena, although equally important in varietal adaptation to flood-prone areas. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Effect of ash on the cold tolerance of rice at seedling stage

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In China, ash is applied either as basal or topdressing to seedbeds during the first cropping season before the onset of low temperature to increase cold tolerance and decrease cold injury at the seedling stage. The potassium-rich ash probably increases cold tolerance, and the dark color of the ash probably absorbs heat and raises water temperature. Two kinds of ash are used: from burnt stove firewood and from burnt straws or grasses with some soil added. Potassium (K₂O) content is 64%. Ash from burnt

straw has more nitrogen.

Three trials were conducted to evaluate whether application of ash could prevent or alleviate discoloration and death of rice seedlings subjected to cold water.

The first experiment tested two varieties — IR8, which is susceptible to low water temperature, and Fujisaka 5, which is resistant. Pulverized rice straw ash and ammonium sulfate were used in four treatments.

Ten rows of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 were sown alternately in each treatment tray. Ten days after soaking, the trays were placed in a circulating-cold-water (12° C) tank with water 2 cm above the soil surface.

The cold tolerance of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 measured by leaf discoloration is shown in the figure. The order of cold

Discoloration scores of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 seedlings grown with different combinations of ash and nitrogen, at different days after start of cold water treatment. IRRI, 1981.

tolerance in all treatments was: ash + N > N > ash > no ash, no N.

The succeeding two trials used only IR8 and added potash in two additional treatments. The order of cold tolerance for the six treatments was K + N > ash + N > K > ash > no ash, no N, no K > N. Leaf discoloration was observed after a day of cold water treatment in plants grown with no ash, no N, no K; with ash and with K. Plants grown in ash + N and K + N did not develop yellowing until 4 or 5 days after the start of the treatment.

Plant height increased despite low water temperature, with significantly higher percentage increases in K+N, and ash + N.

Application of ash or potassium mixed with nitrogen in the seedbed increased plant height, promoted growth, and slowed leaf discoloration, and thus increased cold tolerance during the seedling stage. The treatment is effective both with cold water-susceptible and tolerant varieties. ■